

ISic1614

I.Sicily inscription 1614

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Motya

Place of origin (modern)

Moza

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645071

Bibliography

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1986. Scavi a Mozia - le iscrizioni. Rome. At no.37

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1978. III. Le iscrizioni puniche. In Ciasca, A.(eds.), *Mozia IX*. Rome. pp. 155-159. At no.1

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1614. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI

edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4386205>